

ABOUT THE SMARANDACHE SQUARE'S COMPLEMENTARY FUNCTION

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DEFINITION 1. Let $a: \mathbf{N}^* \rightarrow \mathbf{N}^*$ be a numerical function defined by $a(n) = k$ where k is the smallest natural number such that nk is a perfect square: $nk = s^2$, $s \in \mathbf{N}^*$, which is called the Smarandache square's complementary function.

PROPERTY 1. For every $n \in \mathbf{N}^*$ $a(n^2) = 1$ and for every prime natural number $a(p) = p$.

PROPERTY 2. Let n be a composite natural number and $n = p_{i_1}^{\alpha_{i_1}} \cdot p_{i_2}^{\alpha_{i_2}} \cdots p_{i_r}^{\alpha_{i_r}}$, $0 < p_{i_1} < p_{i_2} < \cdots < p_{i_r}$, $\alpha_{i_1}, \alpha_{i_2}, \dots, \alpha_{i_r} \in \mathbf{N}$ it's prime factorization. Then

$$a(n) = p_{i_1}^{\beta_{i_1}} \cdot p_{i_2}^{\beta_{i_2}} \cdots p_{i_r}^{\beta_{i_r}} \text{ where } \beta_{i_j} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \alpha_{i_j} \text{ is an odd natural number} \\ 0 & \text{if } \alpha_{i_j} \text{ is an even natural number} \end{cases} \quad j = \overline{1, r}.$$

If we take into account of the above definition of the function a , it is easy to prove both the properties.

PROPERTY 3. $\frac{1}{n} \leq \frac{a(n)}{n} \leq 1$, for every $n \in \mathbf{N}^*$ where a is the above defined function.

Proof. It is easy to see that $1 \leq a(n) \leq n$ for every $n \in \mathbf{N}^*$, so the property holds.

CONSEQUENCE. $\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{a(n)}{n}$ diverges.

PROPERTY 4. The function $a: \mathbf{N}^* \rightarrow \mathbf{N}^*$ is multiplicative:

$$a(x \cdot y) = a(x) \cdot a(y) \text{ for every } x, y \in \mathbf{N}^* \text{ which } (x, y) = 1$$

Proof. For $x = 1 = y$ we have $(x, y) = 1$ and $a(1 \cdot 1) = a(1) \cdot a(1)$. Let $x = p_{i_1}^{\alpha_{i_1}} \cdot p_{i_2}^{\alpha_{i_2}} \cdots p_{i_r}^{\alpha_{i_r}}$ and $y = q_{j_1}^{\gamma_{j_1}} \cdot q_{j_2}^{\gamma_{j_2}} \cdots q_{j_s}^{\gamma_{j_s}}$ be the prime factorization of x and y , respectively, and $x \cdot y \neq 1$. Because $(x, y) = 1$ we have $p_{i_h} \neq q_{j_k}$ for every $h = \overline{1, r}$ and $k = \overline{1, s}$. Then,

$$a(x) = p_{i_1}^{\beta_1} \cdot p_{i_2}^{\beta_2} \cdots p_{i_r}^{\beta_r} \quad \text{where } \beta_j = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \alpha_j \text{ is odd} \\ 0 & \text{if } \alpha_j \text{ is even} \end{cases}, j = \overline{1, r},$$

$$a(y) = q_{j_1}^{\delta_1} \cdot q_{j_2}^{\delta_2} \cdots q_{j_s}^{\delta_s} \quad \text{where } \delta_k = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \gamma_k \text{ is odd} \\ 0 & \text{if } \gamma_k \text{ is even} \end{cases}, k = \overline{1, s} \text{ and}$$

$$a(xy) = p_{i_1}^{\beta_1} \cdot p_{i_2}^{\beta_2} \cdots p_{i_r}^{\beta_r} \cdot q_{j_1}^{\delta_1} \cdot q_{j_2}^{\delta_2} \cdots q_{j_s}^{\delta_s} = a(x) \cdot a(y)$$

Property 5. If $(x, y) = 1$, x and y are not perfect squares and $x, y > 1$ the equation $a(x) = a(y)$ has not natural solutions.

Proof. It is easy to see that $x \neq y$. Let $x = \prod_{h=1}^r p_{i_h}^{\alpha_h}$ and $y = \prod_{k=1}^s q_{j_k}^{\gamma_k}$, (where $p_{i_h} \neq q_{j_k}, \forall h = \overline{1, r}, k = \overline{1, s}$ be their prime factorization.

Then $a(x) = \prod_{h=1}^r p_{i_h}^{\beta_h}$ and $a(y) = \prod_{k=1}^s q_{j_k}^{\delta_k}$, where β_h for $h = \overline{1, r}$ and δ_k for $k = \overline{1, s}$ have the above significance, but there exist at least $\beta_h \neq 0$ and $\delta_k \neq 0$. (because x and y are not perfect squares). Then $a(x) \neq a(y)$.

Remark. If $x=1$ from the above equation it results $a(y) = 1$, so y must be a perfect square (analogously for $y=1$).

Consequence. The equation $a(x) = a(x+1)$ has not natural solutions, because for $x > 1$ x and $x+1$ are not both perfect squares and $(x, x+1) = 1$.

Property 6. We have $a(x \cdot y^2) = a(x)$, for every $x, y \in \mathbb{N}^*$.

Proof. If $(x, y) = 1$, then $(x, y^2) = 1$ and using property 4 and property 1 we have $a(x \cdot y^2) = a(x) \cdot a(y^2) = a(x)$. If $(x, y) \neq 1$ we can write: $x = \prod_{h=1}^r p_{i_h}^{\alpha_h} \cdot \prod_{t=1}^n d_t^{\alpha_t}$ and $y = \prod_{k=1}^s q_{j_k}^{\gamma_k} \cdot \prod_{t=1}^n d_t^{\gamma_t}$ where $p_{i_h} \neq d_t, q_{j_k} \neq d_t, p_{i_h} \neq q_{j_k}, \forall h = \overline{1, r}, k = \overline{1, s}, t = \overline{1, n}$, but this

implies $\left(\prod_{h=1}^r p_{i_h}^{\alpha_h} \cdot \prod_{k=1}^s q_{j_k}^{2\gamma_k}, \prod_{t=1}^n d_t^{\alpha_t + 2\gamma_t} \right) = 1$ and

$$\left(\prod_{h=1}^r p_{i_h}^{\alpha_h}, \prod_{k=1}^s q_{j_k}^{2\gamma_k} \right) = 1 \Rightarrow a(xy^2) = a \left(\prod_{h=1}^r p_{i_h}^{\alpha_h} \cdot \prod_{k=1}^s q_{j_k}^{2\gamma_k} \cdot \prod_{t=1}^n d_t^{\alpha_t + 2\gamma_t} \right) =$$

$$a \left(\prod_{h=1}^r p_{i_h}^{\alpha_h} \cdot \prod_{k=1}^s q_{j_k}^{2\gamma_k} \right) \cdot a \left(\prod_{t=1}^n d_t^{\alpha_t + 2\gamma_t} \right) = a \left(\prod_{h=1}^r p_{i_h}^{\alpha_h} \right) \cdot a \left(\prod_{k=1}^s q_{j_k}^{2\gamma_k} \right) \cdot a \left(\prod_{t=1}^n d_t^{\alpha_t + 2\gamma_t} \right)$$

$$a\left(\prod_{h=1}^r p_{i_h}^{\alpha_{i_h}}\right) \cdot a\left(\prod_{t=1}^n d_t^{\alpha_{i_t} - 2\gamma_{i_t}}\right) = a\left(\prod_{h=1}^r p_{i_h}^{\alpha_{i_h}} \cdot \prod_{t=1}^n d_t^{\alpha_{i_t}}\right) = a(x) \text{ because}$$

$$a\left(\prod_{t=1}^n d_t^{\alpha_{i_t} - 2\gamma_{i_t}}\right) = \prod_{t=1}^n d_t^{\beta_{i_t}} = a\left(\prod_{t=1}^n d_t^{\alpha_{i_t}}\right), \text{ where } \beta_{i_t} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \alpha_{i_t} + 2\gamma_{i_t} \text{ is odd} \\ 0 & \text{if } \alpha_{i_t} + 2\gamma_{i_t} \text{ is even} \end{cases}$$

$$= \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \alpha_{i_t} \text{ is odd} \\ 0 & \text{if } \alpha_{i_t} \text{ is even} \end{cases}$$

Consequence 1. For every $x \in \mathbf{N}^*$ and $n \in \mathbf{N}$, $a(x^n) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } n \text{ is even} \\ a(x) & \text{if } n \text{ is odd} \end{cases}$

Consequence 2. If $\frac{x}{y} = \frac{m^2}{n^2}$ where $\frac{m}{n}$ is a simplified fraction, then $a(x) = a(y)$. It is easy to prove this, because $x = km^2$ and $y = kn^2$ and using the above property we have: $a(x) = a(km^2) = a(k) = a(kn^2) = a(y)$.

Property 7. The sumatory numerical function of the function a is $F(n) = \prod_{j=1}^k (H(\alpha_{i_j})(p_{i_j} + 1) + \frac{1 + (-1)^{\alpha_{i_j}}}{2})$ where the prime factorization of n is $n = p_h^{\alpha_h} \cdot p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_k^{\alpha_k}$ and $H(\alpha)$ is the number of the odd numbers which are smaller than α .

Proof. The sumatory numerical function of a is defined as $F(n) = \sum_{d|n} a(d)$, because $(p_1^{\alpha_1}, \prod_{t=2}^k p_{i_t}^{\alpha_{i_t}}) = 1$ we can use the property 4 and we obtain:

$$F(n) = \left(\sum_{d_1 | p_h^{\alpha_h}} a(d_1) \right) \cdot \left(\sum_{d_2 | p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_k^{\alpha_k}} a(d_2) \right) \text{ and so on, making a finite number of steps we obtain}$$

$$F(n) = \prod_{j=1}^k F(p_{i_j}^{\alpha_{i_j}}). \text{ But we observe that}$$

$$F(p^\alpha) = \begin{cases} \frac{\alpha}{2}(p+1) + 1 & \text{if } \alpha \text{ is an even number} \\ \left(\left[\frac{\alpha}{2} \right] + 1 \right) (p+1) & \text{if } \alpha \text{ is an odd number} \end{cases}$$

where p is a prime number.

If we take into account of the definition of $H(\alpha)$ we find

$$H(\alpha) = \begin{cases} \frac{\alpha}{2} & \text{if } \alpha \text{ is even} \\ \left[\frac{\alpha}{2} \right] + 1 & \text{if } \alpha \text{ is odd} \end{cases} \text{ so we can write } F(p^\alpha) = H(\alpha) \cdot (p+1) + \frac{1 + (-1)^\alpha}{2},$$

$$\text{therefore: } F(n) = \prod_{j=1}^k (H(\alpha_{i_j})(p_{i_j} + 1) + \frac{1 + (-1)^{\alpha_{i_j}}}{2}).$$

In the sequel we study some equations which involve the function a .

1) Find the solutions of the equation: $xa(x)=m$, where $x, m \in \mathbb{N}^*$.

If m is not a perfect square then the above equation has not solutions.

If m is a perfect square, $m = z^2, z \in \mathbb{N}^*$, then we have to give the solutions of the equation $xa(x) = z^2$.

Let $z = p_{i_1}^{2\alpha_1} \cdot p_{i_2}^{2\alpha_2} \cdots p_{i_k}^{2\alpha_k}$ be the prime factorization of z . Then $xa(x) = p_{i_1}^{2\alpha_1} \cdot p_{i_2}^{2\alpha_2} \cdots p_{i_k}^{2\alpha_k}$, so taking account of the definition of the function a , the equation has the following solutions:
 $x_1^{(0)} = p_{i_1}^{2\alpha_1} \cdot p_{i_2}^{2\alpha_2} \cdots p_{i_k}^{2\alpha_k}$ (because $a(x_1^{(0)}) = 1$), $x_1^{(1)} = p_{i_1}^{2\alpha_1-1} \cdot p_{i_2}^{2\alpha_2} \cdots p_{i_k}^{2\alpha_k}$ (because $a(x_1^{(1)}) = p_{i_1}$),
 $x_2^{(1)} = p_{i_1}^{2\alpha_1} \cdot p_{i_2}^{2\alpha_2-1} \cdot p_{i_3}^{2\alpha_3} \cdots p_{i_k}^{2\alpha_k}$ (because $a(x_2^{(1)}) = p_{i_2}$), ...,
 $x_k^{(1)} = p_{i_1}^{2\alpha_1} \cdot p_{i_2}^{2\alpha_2} \cdots p_{i_k}^{2\alpha_k-1}$ (because $a(x_k^{(1)}) = p_{i_k}$), then $x_t^{(2)} = \frac{z^2}{p_{i_t} \cdot p_{i_n}}$,

$j_1 \neq j_2, j_1, j_2 \in \{i_1, \dots, i_k\}, t = \overline{1, C_k^2}$ (because $a(x_t^{(2)}) = p_{i_{j_1}} \cdot p_{i_{j_2}}$), and, in an analogue way,

$x_t^{(3)}, t \in \overline{1, C_k^3}$ has as values $\frac{z^2}{p_{i_{j_1}} \cdot p_{i_{j_2}} \cdot p_{i_{j_3}}}$, where $j_1, j_2, j_3 \in \{i_1, \dots, i_k\}$

$j_1 \neq j_2, j_2 \neq j_3, j_3 \neq j_1$, and so on, $x_1^{(k)} = \frac{z^2}{p_{i_1} \cdot p_{i_2} \cdots p_{i_k}} = \frac{z^2}{z} = z$. So the above equation has

$1 + C_k^1 + C_k^2 + \cdots + C_k^k = 2^k$ different solutions where k is the number of the prime divisors of m .

2) Find the solutions of the equation: $xa(x) + ya(y) = za(z), x, y, z \in \mathbb{N}^*$.

Proof. We note $xa(x) = m^2, ya(y) = n^2$ and $za(z) = s^2, x, y, z \in \mathbb{N}^*$ and the equation

$$m^2 + n^2 = s^2, m, n, s \in \mathbb{N}^* \quad (*)$$

has the following solutions: $m = u^2 - v^2, n = 2uv, s = u^2 + v^2, u > v > 0, (u, v) = 1$ and u and v have different evenes.

If (m, n, s) as above is a solution, then $(\alpha m, \alpha n, \alpha s), \alpha \in \mathbb{N}^*$ is also a solution of the equation (*).

If (m, n, s) is a solution of the equation (*), then the problem is to find the solutions of the equation $xa(x) = m^2$ and we see from the above problem that there are 2^{k_1} solutions (where k_1 is the number of the prime divisors of m), then the solutions of the equations $ya(y) = n^2$ and respectively $za(z) = s^2$, so the number of the different solutions of the given equations, is $2^{k_1} \cdot 2^{k_2} \cdot 2^{k_3} = 2^{k_1+k_2+k_3}$ (where k_2 and k_3 have the same signifiense as k_1 , but concerning n and s , respectively).

For $\alpha > 1$ we have $xa(x) = \alpha^2 m^2, ya(y) = \alpha^2 n^2, za(z) = \alpha^2 s^2$ and, using an analogue way as above, we find $2^{k_1+k_2+k_3}$ different solutions, where $k_i, i = \overline{1, 3}$ is the number of the prime divisors of $\alpha m, \alpha n$ and αs , respectively.

Remark. In the particular case $u=2, v=1$ we find the solution $(3, 4, 5)$ for (*). So we must find the solutions of the equations $xa(x) = 3^2 \alpha^2, ya(y) = 2^4 \alpha^2$ and $za(z) = 5^2 \alpha^2$, for $\alpha \in \mathbb{N}^*$. Suppose that α has not 2, 3 and 5 as prime factors in this prime factorization $\alpha = p_{i_1}^{2\alpha_1} \cdot p_{i_2}^{2\alpha_2} \cdots p_{i_k}^{2\alpha_k}$. Then we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
xa(x) = 3^2 \alpha^2 \Rightarrow x \in & \left\{ 3^2 \alpha^2, \frac{3^2 \alpha^2}{p_1}, \dots, \frac{3^2 \alpha^2}{p_{i_k}}, \frac{3^2 \alpha^2}{p_1 \cdot p_2}, \dots, \frac{3^2 \alpha^2}{p_{i_{k-1}} \cdot p_{i_k}}, \dots, \frac{3^2 \alpha^2}{p_1 \dots p_{i_{k-1}}}, \dots, \frac{3^2 \alpha^2}{p_2 \dots p_{i_k}} \right\}, \\
& \left. 3^2 \alpha, 3 \alpha^2, \frac{3 \alpha^2}{p_1}, \dots, \frac{3 \alpha^2}{p_{i_k}}, \frac{3 \alpha^2}{p_1 \cdot p_2}, \dots, \frac{3 \alpha^2}{p_{i_{k-1}} \cdot p_{i_k}}, \dots, \frac{3 \alpha^2}{p_1 \dots p_{i_{k-1}}}, \dots, \frac{3 \alpha^2}{p_2 \dots p_{i_k}}, 3 \alpha \right\} \\
ya(y) = 4^2 \alpha^2 \Rightarrow y \in & \left\{ 4^2 \alpha^2, \frac{4^2 \alpha^2}{p_1}, \dots, \frac{4^2 \alpha^2}{p_{i_k}}, \frac{4^2 \alpha^2}{p_1 \cdot p_2}, \dots, \frac{4^2 \alpha^2}{p_{i_{k-1}} \cdot p_{i_k}}, \dots, \frac{4^2 \alpha^2}{p_1 \dots p_{i_{k-1}}}, \dots, \frac{4^2 \alpha^2}{p_2 \dots p_{i_k}} \right\}, \\
& \left. 4^2 \alpha, 8 \alpha^2, \frac{8 \alpha^2}{p_1}, \dots, \frac{8 \alpha^2}{p_{i_k}}, \frac{8 \alpha^2}{p_1 \cdot p_2}, \dots, \frac{8 \alpha^2}{p_{i_{k-1}} \cdot p_{i_k}}, \dots, \frac{8 \alpha^2}{p_1 \dots p_{i_{k-1}}}, \dots, \frac{8 \alpha^2}{p_2 \dots p_{i_k}}, 8 \alpha \right\} \\
za(z) = 5^2 \alpha^2 \Rightarrow z \in & \left\{ 5^2 \alpha^2, \frac{5^2 \alpha^2}{p_1}, \dots, \frac{5^2 \alpha^2}{p_{i_k}}, \frac{5^2 \alpha^2}{p_1 \cdot p_2}, \dots, \frac{5^2 \alpha^2}{p_{i_{k-1}} \cdot p_{i_k}}, \dots, \frac{5^2 \alpha^2}{p_1 \dots p_{i_{k-1}}}, \dots, \frac{5^2 \alpha^2}{p_2 \dots p_{i_k}} \right\}, \\
& \left. 5^2 \alpha, 5 \alpha^2, \frac{5 \alpha^2}{p_1}, \dots, \frac{5 \alpha^2}{p_{i_k}}, \frac{5 \alpha^2}{p_1 \cdot p_2}, \dots, \frac{5 \alpha^2}{p_{i_{k-1}} \cdot p_{i_k}}, \dots, \frac{5 \alpha^2}{p_1 \dots p_{i_{k-1}}}, \dots, \frac{5 \alpha^2}{p_2 \dots p_{i_k}}, 5 \alpha \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

So any triplet (x_0, y_0, z_0) with x_0, y_0 and z_0 arbitrary of above corresponding values, is a solution for the equation (for example $(9, 16, 25)$, is a solution).

Definition. The triplets which are the solutions of the equation $xa(x) + ya(y) = za(z)$, $x, y, z \in \mathbf{Z}^*$ we call MIV numbers.

3) Find the natural numbers x such that $a(x)$ is a three - cornered, a squared and a pentagonal number.

Proof. Because 1 is the only number which is at the same time a three - cornered, a squared and a pentagonal number, then we must find the solutions of the equation $a(x)=1$, therefore x is any perfect square.

4) Find the solutions of the equation: $\frac{1}{xa(x)} + \frac{1}{ya(y)} = \frac{1}{za(z)}$, $x, y, z \in \mathbf{N}^*$.

Proof. We have $xa(x) = m^2, ya(y) = n^2, za(z) = s^2$, $m, n, s \in \mathbf{N}^*$.

The equation $\frac{1}{m^2} + \frac{1}{n^2} = \frac{1}{s^2}$ has the solutions:

$$m = t(u^2 + v^2)2uv$$

$$n = t(u^2 + v^2)(u^2 - v^2)$$

$$s = t(u^2 - v^2)2uv,$$

$u > v$, $(u, v) = 1$, u and v have different evenness and $t \in \mathbb{N}^*$, so we have

$$xa(x) = t^2(u^2 + v^2)^2 4u^2v^2$$

$$ya(y) = t^2(u^2 + v^2)^2(u^2 - v^2)^2$$

$$za(z) = t^2(u^2 - v^2)^2 4u^2v^2$$

and we find x , y and z in the same way which is indicated in the first problem.

For example, if $u=2$, $v=1$, $t=1$ we have

$m=20$, $n=15$, $s=12$, so we must find the solutions of the following equations:

$$xa(x) = 20^2 = 2^4 \cdot 5^2 \Rightarrow x \in \{2^3 \cdot 5^2 = 200, 2^4 \cdot 5 = 80, 2^3 \cdot 5 = 40, 2^4 \cdot 5^2 = 400\}$$

$$ya(y) = 15^2 = 3^2 \cdot 5^2 \Rightarrow y \in \{15, 45, 75, 225\}$$

$$za(z) = 12^2 = 2^4 \cdot 3^2 \Rightarrow z \in \{24, 48, 72, 144\}$$

Therefore for this particular values of u , v and t we find $4 \cdot 4 \cdot 4 = 2^2 \cdot 2^2 \cdot 2^2 = 2^6 = 64$ solutions. (because $k_1 = k_2 = k_3 = 2$)

5) Find the solutions of the equation: $a(x) + a(y) + a(z) = a(x)a(y)a(z)$, $x, y, z \in \mathbb{N}^*$.

Proof. If $a(x) = m$, $a(y) = n$ and $a(z) = s$, the equation $m + n + s = m \cdot n \cdot s$, $m, n, s \in \mathbb{N}^*$ has a solutions the permutations of the set $\{1, 2, 3\}$ so we have:

$$a(x) = 1 \Rightarrow x \text{ must be a perfect square, therefore } x = u^2, u \in \mathbb{N}^*$$

$$a(y) = 2 \Rightarrow y = 2v^2, v \in \mathbb{N}^*$$

$$a(z) = 3 \Rightarrow z = 3t^2, t \in \mathbb{N}^*$$

Therefore the solutions are the permutation of the sets $\{u^2, 2v^2, 3t^2\}$ where $u, v, t \in \mathbb{N}^*$.

6) Find the solutions of the equation $Aa(x) + Ba(y) + Ca(z) = 0$, $A, B, C \in \mathbb{Z}^*$.

Proof. If we note $a(x) = u$, $a(y) = v$, $a(z) = t$ we must find the solutions of the equation $Au + Bv + Ct = 0$.

Using the method of determinants we have:

$$\begin{vmatrix} A & B & C \\ A & B & C \\ m & n & s \end{vmatrix} = 0, \quad \forall m, n, s \in \mathbb{Z} \Rightarrow A(Bs - Cn) + B(Cm - As) + C(An - Bm) = 0, \text{ and it}$$

is known that the only solutions are

$$\begin{aligned} u &= Bs - Cn \\ v &= Cm - As \\ t &= An - Bm, \quad \forall m, n, s \in \mathbb{Z} \end{aligned}$$

so, we have

$$\begin{aligned} a(x) &= Bs - Cn \\ a(y) &= Cm - As \\ a(z) &= An - Bm \end{aligned} \text{ and now we know to find } x, y \text{ and } z.$$

Example. If we have the following equation: $2a(x) - 3a(y) - a(z) = 0$, using the above result we must find (with the above mentioned method) the solutions of the equations:

$$a(x) = -3s + n$$

$$a(y) = -m - 2s$$

$$a(z) = 2n + 3m, \quad m, n \text{ and } s \in \mathbf{Z}.$$

For $m = -1, n = 2, s = 0 : a(x) = 2, a(y) = 1, a(z) = 1$ so, the solution in this case is $(2\alpha^2, \beta^2, \gamma^2), \alpha, \beta, \gamma \in \mathbf{Z}^*$. For the another values of m, n, s we find the corresponding solutions.

7) The same problem for the equation $Aa(x) + Ba(y) = C, \quad A, B, C \in \mathbf{Z}$.

Proof. $Aa(x) + Ba(y) - C = 0 \Leftrightarrow Aa(x) + Ba(y) + (-C)a(z) = 0$ with $a(z) = 1$ so we must have $An - Bm = 1$. If n_0 and m_0 are solutions of this equation ($An_0 - Bm_0 = 1$) it remains us to find the solutions of the following equations:

$$a(x) = Bs + Cn_0$$

$$a(y) = -Cm_0 - As, \quad s \in \mathbf{Z}, \text{ but we know how to find them.}$$

Example. If we have the equation $2a(x) - 3a(y) = 5, \quad x, y \in \mathbf{N}^*$ using the above results, we get: $A=2, B=-3, C=-5$ and $a(z) = 1 = 2n + 3m$. The solutions are $m = 2k + 1$ and $n = -1 - 3k, \quad k \in \mathbf{Z}$. For the particular value $k = -1$ we have $m_0 = -1$ and $n_0 = 2$ so we find $a(x) = -3 + 5 \cdot 2 = 10 - 3s$ and $a(y) = -5(-1) - 2s = 5 - 2s$.

$$\text{If } s_0 = 0 \text{ we find } a(x) = 10 \Rightarrow x = 10u^2, \quad u \in \mathbf{Z}^*$$

$$a(y) = 5 \Rightarrow y = 5v^2, \quad v \in \mathbf{Z}^* \text{ and so on.}$$

8) Find the solutions of the equation: $a(x) = ka(y) \quad k \in \mathbf{N}^* \quad k > 1$.

Proof. If k has in his prime factorization a factor which has an exponent ≥ 2 , then the problem has not solutions.

If $k = p_{i_1} \cdot p_{i_2} \cdots p_{i_r}$ and the prime factorization of $a(y)$ is $a(y) = q_{j_1} \cdot q_{j_2} \cdots q_{j_u}$, then we have solutions only in the case $p_{i_1}, p_{i_2}, \dots, p_{i_r} \notin \{q_{j_1}, q_{j_2}, \dots, q_{j_u}\}$.

This implies that $a(x) = p_{i_1} \cdot p_{i_2} \cdots p_{i_r} \cdot q_{j_1} \cdot q_{j_2} \cdots q_{j_u}$, so we have the solutions

$$x = p_{i_1} \cdot p_{i_2} \cdots p_{i_r} \cdot q_{j_1} \cdot q_{j_2} \cdots q_{j_u} \cdot \alpha^2$$

$$y = q_{j_1} \cdot q_{j_2} \cdots q_{j_u} \cdot \beta^2, \quad \alpha, \beta \in \mathbf{Z}^*.$$

9) Find the solutions of the equation $a(x) = x$ (the fixed points of the function a).

Proof. Obviously, $a(1) = 1$. Let $x > 1$ and let $x = p_1^{\alpha_1} \cdot p_2^{\alpha_2} \cdots p_r^{\alpha_r}, \quad \alpha_j \geq 1, \text{ for } j = \overline{1, r}$ be the prime factorization of x . Then $a(x) = p_1^{\beta_1} \cdot p_2^{\beta_2} \cdots p_r^{\beta_r}$ and $\beta_j \leq 1$ for $j = \overline{1, r}$. Because $a(x) = x$ this implies that $\alpha_j = \beta_j = 1, \quad \forall j \in \overline{1, r}$, therefore $x = p_1 \cdot p_2 \cdots p_r$, where $p_{i_j}, \quad j = \overline{1, r}$ are prime numbers.

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